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EMERGING KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT, HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR : OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Over the past several years there have been intensive discussions about the importance of knowledge management within our society and in particular within the organization. There is increasing recognition that organizational knowledge represents the firm's 'intellectual capital' and is a source of both current and future earnings. As Peter Ducker put it, "Knowledge is and will be the basic economic resource". In simple words, the key function of management is to engineer and manage knowledge. Management of organization for harnessing man-power strategy must encourage new knowledge to come forward. Everyone's knowledge must be tapped. Knowledge that one doesn't understand must be managed and people must be encouraged to learn. Indeed, Ducker (1999) has gone as far as to suggest that a firm's ability to recognize and manage organizational knowledge will be the single most important determinant of firm survival.

It is in this given perspective, the objective of this paper is to explore the key component of an effective system to leverage knowledge for an integration and sharing of the benefits to promote the progressive base of Indian business organizations in terms of asset based inflow of tangible resources in connection with physical, financial and information infrastructure in general and intangible resources of the human resource development and the management of knowledge in particular for managing, maintaining, regulating and sustaining the overall productivity and profitability as well as the status quo of the corporate sector both in national and international markets

Key Words: knowledge management, component, Indian business organizations

Introduction:

Building human capital and managing knowledge have been the fundamental issues in the new forms of management of business firms, based on a central role for knowledge production and the ability of managerial skill to human resource development to invest and innovate by creating new knowledge and ideas in products, process and technology-in order to ensure that the right knowledge is brought to bear at the right time. It becomes imperative for Indian business organizations go global have to look at knowledge management practice to capture knowledge beyond local boundaries. Knowledge management will go beyond the boundaries of individual corporations to provide a global rather than a local picture. For companies like TCS, Tata, Wipro Limited (India), Infosys Limited (India), Reliance Industry Ltd, ICICI Bank, Patni Computer System, Aditya Birla Group, Satyam Computers Service Ltd in private sector and National Thermal Power Corporation as well as National Gas Corporation in public sector (under taken in this study) and others that operate in dozens of countries, knowledge management can give them an edge in the competitive software and other respective fields of services market. In recent years, the Indian strategic business firms having a growing capitalism are now in the league of the growing world business organization for larger investment to foreign destination and making sharing foundation to face the opportunities and challenges of the fundamentals of HRM and the knowledge economy.

In the light of the changing dimensions of managing knowledge, developing HRM and making a road map for constant growth and development of organization as per the global order of knowledge management. This paper, therefore: identifies all most all the pillars of the emerging fundamentals of knowledge economy as a new imperative for human resource management and the new challenges and opportunities for changing dynamics of modern organizations. The paper is divided into three sections. While **section I** concentrates on the fundamentals of knowledge management, **section II** devotes attention to human resource management and **section III** finally examines the new fundamentals of modern corporate sector in the light of changing dynamics of global order of knowledge management.

Section I

Fundamentals of Knowledge Management

The knowledge revolution marks a fundamental shift in human resource development beyond the limitations imposed by *material processes* toward the unlimited, indeed, infinite creative potential, of *human processes*. In fact, this shift is really not as unusual as we may have thought. All resources, even land and minerals, are products of the human mind. Anything becomes a resource only when the human mind recognizes a valuable use for it. As futurist Alvin Tofler has documented, the shift from physical power to wealth power to mind power is an evolution in the foundations of the global economy. It marks a fundamental shift in the character of social evolution. In its essence, development is a human process that is determined by the response of people to their external environment. Development is, therefore; a means through which human beings become aware of opportunities and challenges, formulate responses, make decisions, and initiate organized actions. No matter how great the opportunity or how dire the necessity, without that knowledge no adaptive response occurs. Knowledge is fundamental to each step in the development process. It is essential for creating awareness of opportunities and challenges, evaluating alternatives, formulating responses, effective planning, organizing initiatives, and implementing those initiatives as the part the parcel of human resource development.

As a practical matter, organizations need to manage knowledge both as object and process. Knowledge management is a practice that addresses the need for information that is required for making effective decisions. If this information is structured, the same can be translated into knowledge by applying a set of predefined rules¹.

The application of Knowledge Management in the organization results from the business strategy whose objectives and practices are specified in the information strategy and in the human resource strategy. The information strategy defines objectives and practices for managing information resources (i.e. information systems and their information). It determines the way of managing explicit knowledge in the organization. The human resource strategy defines objectives and practices for managing human resources (i.e. workers and their knowledge). It determines the way of managing tacit knowledge in the organization. The application of Knowledge Management in the organization leads to efficient and effective management of information and human resources and so leads to efficient and effective management of explicit and tacit knowledge. It is to be understood not as an occupation, but as a dimension of creativity and innovativeness of work in finding existing knowledge and generating new knowledge

Figure - 1

Practices and Processes Used in Knowledge Management.

Source: Computed From the Various Studies.

. There are at least eight categories of knowledge that organization may use in activating HRM².

Figure - 2

Phases of Knowledge Management

Source: As On Figure - 1

There are many definitions of knowledge management but this study combines the KM and OM literature along with HRM to define KM as the process of selectively applying knowledge from previous experiences of decision-making to current and future decision making activities with the purpose of improving the organization's effectiveness, on the one hand, and innovative as well as creative development of HR, on the other. The figure 3 presents and interrelation between Org. Learning, KM and OM to focus the central point of HR Systems & Processes.

Figure - 3

Source: Computed from Various Studies.

On the whole, it may be added that Knowledge has become the most important capital in the present age and hence the success of any organization as well as society lie in harnessing it. The knowledge societies first realize the importance of knowledge and also the importance of proper knowledge distribution, sharing and building for social development and organizational expansion, and promotion. It is, therefore; apparently clear that the knowledge and information are vital components of the formation of any society because every society is formed around

some shared concepts. Thus organization need people, and people need organization. Such mutual relation exists therefore one without another has no possibilities to achieve its objectives. Ducker and Miller (1998)³ depict mutual relation and requirements among the enterprise and employees. Hence, it is important to highlight the fundamentals of changing paradigm of modern organization and the knowledge management.

Section II

Knowledge Economy and Human Resource Management: Opportunities and Challenges

Human resource management is the central point in between knowledge management and organizational growth and development. The efficient and effective human resource management (HRM) and the use of proven HRM practices in job design, recruitment, selection and orientation, performance management compensation, training and development can help the organization and its managers to create conditions for efficient and effective management of workers and their knowledge in the organization. In view of voluntary and mutual creation, sharing and use of knowledge in the organization it is important.

It is no longer enough for HRM to maintain a narrow operational focus, view its activities as confined to the boundaries of its own organization, or limit itself only to traditional human resource (HR) responsibilities. To continue as it has in the past will relegate HRM to increasing irrelevance and likely outsourcing in the attainment of the future. Although many familiar HRM activities are necessary, they are increasingly distant from a firm's direct value creating processes. By taking a new perspective on how HRM can create strategic capability and provide value for customer's HR can increase its importance in the twenty first century organization.⁴

Thus, HRM, HRIS and MPP for any business organization in the context of the knowledge economy at present face a new imperative in the present century from the angle of: (a) building strategic capabilities (b) expanding its boundaries and (c) managing its roles to ensure HRIS and the MPP more and more efficiently to face the opportunities and challenges of the knowledge economy in the global order of knowledge revaluation. It's time for companies to develop a strategy for knowledge work-one that not only provides a clearer view of the types of

information that workers need to do their jobs but also recognizes that the application of technology across the organization must vary considerably, according to the tasks different knowledge workers perform. Experimentations on divergent paths for using and applying both the free access and structured knowledge work should be perform and its productivity improved. There is also some common understanding to managerial experts to enhance knowledge workers productivity by making a tradeoff between these two models for harnessing the productive power of knowledge workers. Some organizations combine these two sets of operations to HRM and HRIS as hybrid approach.

Figure - 4

Different types of knowledge workers require different kinds of support technologies.

Source: Computed from T.H Davenport; (2011) "Rethinking Knowledge Work: A Strategic Approach" McKinsey & Company, P-9

T.H Davenport (2011)⁵ held the view that knowledge worker's information needs vary. Hence key to better productivity is applying technology more precisely. He has made it clear that knowledge work generally falls into one of four clusters, each with its own characteristics. These four knowledge work classifications are shaped by two factors: the work's degree of complexity (x-axis) and the level of interdependence among workers who carry out a task (y-axis). Leaders

can use this taxonomy as a guide to determine whether a structured, free, or hybrid approach best fits a given job.

At least, there are four kinds of models as how to use and apply the knowledge workers with different kinds of supporting technologies. Figure - 4 exhibits different types of knowledge workers and their requirement in getting different kinds of support from the technologies.

The level of interdependence between the traction cell, integration cell, expert cell and finally the collaboration cell as shown in figure 4 depends on the classification of work and their operational roles that vary considerably across organization. Hence, it is critical to ensure that at least some knowledge workers and executive must understand how the structured system and provision tools and the free access tools work so that they should pull the plug on structured system as well as the free access system and may return to human judgment in identifying such mismatches that can save the organization from losing lots of unproductive investment.

We live in a world where knowledge-based work is expanding rapidly. So is the application of technology to almost every business process and job. But to date, high end knowledge workers have largely remained free to use only the technology they personally find useful. It's time to time to think about how to make them more productive by imposing a bit more structure. This combination of technology and structure, along with a bit of managerial discretion in applying them to knowledge work, may well produce a revolution in the jobs that cost and matter the most to contemporary organizations⁶.

For knowledge management to be effective, the training department and information technology department must collaborate (Zielinski, 2000)⁷. Training can help develop the culture as well as the content and learning strategies. Information technology develops the system for accessing, sharing, and string knowledge and delivering training. According to Kumpikaite (2004)⁸ human resource development is process, covering training of new employees, their adaptation, professional development, re-skilling, career development and reserve formation, in order to improve and develop personal and team work performance, having combined

organizational and personal employees' objectives and needs, and allowing employees to continually develop, thus achieving the best as possible results of organization.

Section III

The Fundamentals of Changing Paradigm of Modern Organization And Knowledge Management

Literature on new approach to organization as system is vast growing. A number of management theorists have contributed to the evolution of knowledge management and the changing fundamentals of new form of modern organization. Among them such notables as Peter Drucker, Paul Strassmann, and Peter Senge in the United States. Drucker and Strassmann have stressed the growing importance of information and explicit knowledge as organizational resources, and Senge has focused on the "learning organization," a cultural dimension of managing knowledge. Chris Argyris, Christopher Bartlett, and Dorothy Leonard-Barton of Harvard Business School have examined various facets of managing knowledge. In fact, Leonard-Barton's well-known case study of Chaparral Steel, a company which has had an effective knowledge management strategy in place since the mid-1970s, inspired the research documented in her *Wellsprings of Knowledge — Building and Sustaining Sources of Innovation* (Harvard Business School Press, 1995). Goncharov (1999)⁹, Sakalas (1996)¹⁰ form new approach to the organization as system-in-modern organization human being acts not only as the system element, but he can be treated as environment as well. Simonsen (1997)¹¹ gives old and new paradigms of the organization, where we can clearly see the influence of environmental changes. He states, that environmental changes require from employees fast acquiring of new skills and their development, flexibility, continual learning, ability to control self-development and career. Modern conditions require that individual would co-ordinate own objectives and career plans with organizational needs and directives. Therefore, although technological advantages allow increasing organization competitiveness, in nowadays-informative society employee well developed able to adapt to appropriate work requirement is treated as the substantial source of progressive organization¹².

Table - 1

Old and New Paradigms of Organization

Old Paradigm	New Paradigm
Paternalistic	Authorities
Development goes by virtue of managers	Partnership in employees development
Career path is defined	Versatile movement on career
Closed plans of top level managers	All employees are involved into self development
The information Communication is absent	Open information about the organization objectives, needs
Compensation rewards upward moves	Remuneration depends on contribution to the organization.

Source: Computed from various studies on the old and new dynamics of organization

Kanter (2000)¹³ provides six important features, by which modern organizations are characterized:

- New principles of personnel selection are seen;
- New organization from vertical to horizontal;
- Organizations shifts from homogeneity to diversity. In organization on equal rights work persons of different social and cultural categories;
- From command right to relations: new control sources are formed;
- From company to project: new loyalty;
- From organization capital to reputation capital: career forming.

Several managerial experts have originated the concept and the framework of learning organization. According to Peddler, Burgoyne and Boydell (1991)¹⁴, the learning company can be thought of as a 'vision of what might be possible'. Authors state that this can only happen as a result of learning on a total organization level.

The nature of learning organization is defined by Pedler, Burgoyne and Boydell (1989, 1991) and Burgoyne (1992) as:, An organization that facilitates the learning of all its members and continuously transforms itself (Pedler, Burgoyne and Boydell, 1991)¹⁵, and is described by Pedler, Burgoyne and Boydell (1989)¹⁶ as the one, which:

- 'Has a climate in which individual members are encouraged to learn and to develop their full potential.
- Extends this learning culture to include customers, suppliers and other significant holders wherever possible.

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- Makes human resource development strategy central to business policy so that the process of individual and organization learning becomes a major business activity.
- A continuous process of organizational transformation harnessing the fruits of individual learning to make fundamental changes in assumptions, goals, norms and operating procedures on the basis of the internal drive to self direction and not reactively to external pressures.

The definitions reveal that company engaged in improvement processes and which attempts to build in these mechanisms, is not necessarily a learning organization. The essential features in provide definitions of a learning organization has been presented in Table 2.2 These elements are of course considerably generalized, but they, nevertheless, give an idea of which processes should occur in a organization.

Table – 2 Key Features of a Learning Organization

Feature	Description
Continuous learning and improvements	Employees share learning with each other and use job as a basis for applying and creating knowledge.
Knowledge Generation and Sharing	Systems are developed for creating, capturing, and sharing knowledge
Systematic changes	Employees are encouraged to think in new ways of opportunities for making relationships and feedback loops, and test assumptions.
Learning Culture	Learning is rewarded, promoted, and supported by managers as company's objectives.
Encouragement of Flexibility and Experimentation	Employees are free to take risks, innovate, explore new ideas, try new processes, and develop new products and services.
Valuing of Employees	System and environment focus on ensuring the development and well-being of every employee.

Source: Vilmante Kumpikaite; Human Resource Development in the Knowledge Society, *Ekonomika ir vadyba* 2007 P-124.

From the above features as reflected in table 2.2, it appears that learning organization emphasizes knowledge management and training as one parts of a system designed to create intellectual capital. In learning organization, training processes are carefully scrutinized and aligned with company goals. It should be noticed that essence of the idea of the learning organization is not training, but self-development. Learning organization emphasizes that learning occurs not only at the individual employee level (as we traditionally think of learning), but also at the group and organizational levels. If the company aims to place itself in such a position, it needs to have a process by which the organization as a whole changes its methods, practices and procedures and by this means transforms itself into a learning organization (Burgoyne 1992)¹⁷. It shows the importance of human resource development.

There is the fundamental distinction between knowledge and physical work. It is relatively easy to coerce and control physical labor that by definition is observable and measurable. Indeed, by applying the appropriate levels of job design and control, and employing organization can fairly easily ensure that employees are operating at 'peak efficiently' In contrast, knowledge work is fundamentally unobservable one observes the outcomes not the process of knowledge work. As a result, the organization cannot impose external controls. Rather, the organization must focus on creating the conditions for the enhanced performance of knowledge work by enhancing employee ability motivation and opportunity provide these conditions.

Hence, there is a need for enhancing the productivity of knowledge workers for which a learning organization has to facilitate the condition at organizational level by enhancing employees' ability, motivation and opportunities as a whole in the systematic and scientific methods of motivational practices and procedures.

Indeed the purposes for development fall into two manjor areas (1) the organization and (2) the individual but these need not be mutually exclusive. Indeed, it is desirable that they overlap, but no attempt should be made to force that relationship (Kumpikaite, 2007)¹⁸.

An organization that wants to be prepared to move with new ideas and trends needs a work force that is ready to learn anything new that comes along employees may not always have

training or education needs, but participating in human resource development activities can keep the work force in a learning mode (Kumpikaite and Sakalas, 2007)¹⁹.

On the basis of above observations provided by many managerial thinkers, a proposed model of knowledge use in organization may be constructed with rationale also for enhancing conditions in an organizations work culture by creating a constant focus on employees ability, motivation by providing them the opportunities as per the changing dynamics of knowledge work and use in organization

Figure- 5
A Model of Knowledge Work and its Use in Organizational Behavior

Source: E.Kevin Kelloway and Julian Barling; Knowledge work as organizational behavior. p-94

As shown in the figure 2.4 that there are three central characteristics in knowledge work as organization behavior i.e. employee ability, employee motivation and opportunity mediate the relationships between the use of knowledge in organizations and various organizational predictors of knowledge use. Consistent with this mediational view, It may be suggested that changes in organizational practices are likely to affect the use of knowledge in organizations to

the extent that they act to increase employee ability, increase employee motivation or increase employees' opportunity to use their knowledge in the workplace. There are two basic choices organization face in acquiring the competencies they need. Organizations can make the required competencies through training and development or they can buy these competencies through employee selection. However, the promotion of knowledge work in organizations requires going beyond the objective attainment of knowledge or credentials to include employees' perceptions of their skill base and evaluation of their ability to use this knowledge. Research on self-efficacy has confirmed that individuals who see themselves as being efficacious in particular areas (a) cope more effectively with change (Hill et al. 1987)²⁰, (b) perform better on related tasks (Barling and Beattie 1983)²¹, and (c) persist at tasks when faced with adversity (Lent et al 1987)²².

Drucker (1999)²³ emphasizes the role of continuous learning (hence training) in enhancing knowledge workers' productivity. In his identification of organizational practices that create a high performance environment Pfeffer (1998)²⁴ emphasized the role of both rigorous (i.e. skill-based) selection and extensive ongoing investment in employee training. Both practices are suggested here to increase both the ability and motivation of employees to use their knowledge in organizations. Clearly, investment in selection and training increases the ability of employees as organizations select and/or train individuals in specific competencies. However, it is more accurate and more useful to think of employees in a new way: not as assets but as investors'. Hence it is the discretionary, use of knowledge by individuals that leads to organizational growth and survival. Davenport (1999)²⁵ argues that employees are most properly viewed as investors of their intellectual capital. As investors, employees choose whether or not to invest their skills in a given company. Perhaps more to the point, as investors, employees choose when to invest their knowledge, and how much of their knowledge to invest. Moreover, employees choose to withdraw their investment in the workplace when the 'pay-off' falls below acceptable levels. An organization's intellectual capital can only be enhanced by catalysts that encourage these investment decisions. Importantly, simply employing an individual is not a guarantee that the investment will be made. Rather, the organization's task is to stimulate

employee investment by creating the appropriate conditions. Apart from these conditions, Organizational rewards can also enhance or detract from knowledge use in organizations.

On the whole it may be added that knowledge use in organizations must be based on (a) employees with high levels of ability who are (b) motivated to use their knowledge toward organizational ends and (c) given the opportunity to use their knowledge in the workplace. As such, these areas present as the most likely focus of interventions designed to enhance knowledge use in organizations. If Drucker (1999) is correct in his identification of enhancing knowledge workers' productivity as a survival challenge for organizations, then the proposed model targets the most efficacious means of ensuring firm survival and growth.

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